

Evaluating the Effects of Liquidity Management Practices on Performance of SACCOs in Garissa

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Abstract

SACCOs plays a key role in the development of the country through contributing to the economic growth by providing financial services to the citizens. However, the financial institutions face a myriad of challenges that expose them to performance challenges. Ineffective liquidity management practices have been cited as a major challenge in the operations of SACCOs. The study centered on establishing the effects of liquidity management practices on financial performance of SACCOs

in Garissa County in Kenya. The study was anchored on Liquidity Preference Theory. An explanatory research design was adopted. The study targeted 10 SACCOs operating in Garissa County where the units of observation comprised of 115 top, middle and lower management levels. A census approach was employed where all SACCOs were involved in the study. A five point Likert scale questionnaire was adopted in collecting primary data from the target respondents. The collected data was analyzed qualitatively through descriptive and inferential statistics. The statistics were generated by the help of MS Excel and Statistical Package for Social Scientists. The results of the study were displayed in form of tables and figures. Prior collection of data, the study conducted a pilot study on two SACCOs operating in Wajir County to assess the level of validity and reliability of the data collection instrument. Validity was assessed through component factor analysis while Cronbach alpha coefficient value was applied in assessing the reliability level. The regression results revealed that R-value was 0.847 implying existence of a strong relationship between liquidity and SACCO financial performance in Garissa County and its financial management techniques. The study established that liquidity management practices, significantly affects financial performance of Saccos operating in Garissa County as shown Beta values of 0.491. The study recommended that there is a need for the management of the Saccos to enhance liquidity management practices.

1.1 Background of the Study

Financial performance according to Fatihudin and Mochklas (2018) is the extent to which an organization meets or is meeting its financial objectives. Naz *et al.*, (2016) further perceives financial performance as the analysis of financial statements comprising of account summary and

related to expenses, revenues, profits, losses and changes in liabilities and assets. According to Kader and Khan (2020) financial performance is conducted with the aid of financial analysis within the organization. During the assessment of a firm's financial performances, area such as working capital analysis, activity analysis, financial structure analysis and profitability analysis are considered. The analysis

takes two dimensions comprising of dimension of used materials and dimension of operational modes. In both dimensions, the analysis takes is conducted both externally and internally.

In the internal analysis, organizational employees and executives or individuals with access to the books of accounts and other business related information are involved in the analysis. The external analysis entails involving business outsiders such as credit agencies, investors and creditors who bears no access to internal books of accounts but rely on secondary published materials (Butt *et al.*, 2010). Mode of operation dimension entails both vertical and horizontal analysis. In the horizontal analysis, a review and analysis of statements of finances for specific number of years is done. In the vertical financial analysis, a qualitative assessment of relationships between various statements of finances based on particular date and other organizations in the same line is done. In assessing financial performances of organizations, Matsoso and Benedict (2016) advocates for consideration of measures such as growth in sales, ROI (Returns on Invest), ROCE(Return on Capital Employed), ROE(Return on Equity) and returns on sales.

Growth in sales relates to overall improvement in the organizational returns and the organizational capability of attaining equilibrium with surrounding operational environment. Assets returns points to the obtained profits compared with employed total asset and provide an overview of management efficient levels in respect to the usage of assets in attaining profits (Kipkorir *et al.*, 2016). ROI on the other hand points to the investment efficiency or efficiency comparison in respect to various organizational investments. ROCE portrays the firms level of investment profitability while ROE can be viewed as the averaged income when divided by the stakeholders' equity. All these measures can be derived from the financial statements of the organizations and can be utilized in assessing the organizational financial performances. To fully assess the organizational financial performances, Ndungo *et al.*, (2016) advocates for incorporation of non-financial performance measures such as operational efficiencies, service delivery flexibility and organizational dependability.

Financial Performance forms one of the most important objectives of managing finances since one of the crucial roles of financial management is maximizing the wealth of owners. Thus financial

performance is critical in assessing the failure or success of a business. At the initiation stage, a business may not be in a position of generating profits due to expenses and investments involved in the establishment of the business. However, upon business maturity, profits must be produced as a sign that a firm is performing. Kule and Kijjambu (2020) established that performance forms one of the most significant determinants of credit risks for SACCOs.

Benson *et al.*, (2016) stress that a business main aim is not only to generate and increase the levels of sales but also to gain profits. Profits as pointed by the scholars are crucial since it is important for the survival and continuity of business. Low performance culminates to capital underutilization since it contributes to retained earnings thus leading to external capital reliance. An empirical evidence provided by Chamwana and Anyieni(2017) on the relationship between utilization of financial reports and organizational financial performance revealed that respondents utilizing financial reports in assessing financial performance in decision making reasons was significantly better compared to those who failed to utilize the reports.

SACCOs comprise of voluntary associations owned and manned by their members and operated with the aim of promoting members' savings, availing credits to members at low rates of interest and providing other financial products and services (Asratie, 2014). SACCOs are in a position of advancing loans to members at lower interest rates as compared to other financial institutions such as the commercial banks. Additionally, they have the opportunity and capability of reaching clients even in remote areas uncovered by commercial banks such as rural areas thus making them more attractive to customers thus engaging themselves deeply in the financial sectors. According to Olando *et al.*, (2013) SACCOs are associated with intrinsic principles and values of self-responsibility, self-help, equality, democracy, equity and solidarity. In Kenya, SACCOs are supervised and regulated by SASRA and operates under Co-operative Societies Act 2008.

Olando *et al.*, (2013) argues that low levels of profitability posted by SACCOs is not only due to financial mismanagement and governance issues but also due to poor costing strategies aimed at making loans more attractive members. For effective operational of SACCOs, there is a need to put in place measures that aim at maximizing on earnings so as to build enough and firm institutional capital.

Platje(2008) notes that institutional capital aims at ensuring existence of growth and permanence even in turbulent operational environment.

The growth and permanence characteristics of SACCOs that signifies growth can be attained through adoption of the right financial management practices (Ochieng, 2018). Each SACCO imperatively ought to generate adequate income sufficient to cover all operational costs, enhance the institutional dividends and capital. In this perspective, financial practice focuses on solid capital structure, financial stewardship and concise strategy for allocating funds. The current study sought to establish how effective financial management contributes to financial performance of SACCOs focusing on Garissa County.

Statement of the Problem

A report from SASRA(2020) revealed that majority of SACCOs that collapsed in Kenya had adopted inefficient financial reporting practices that culminated into delivering unsatisfactory reports to relevant bodies such as regulators and stakeholders. This resulted into proactive decision making by the bodies on the basis of incomprehensive and inconsistent financial reports in areas of cash flows, capital, financial positions and incomes. Through the adoption of relevant practices on financial management, both the public stakeholders can assess the SACCOs performance including that of its managers Olando *et al.*, (2013). The current study sought to establish the financial management practices that affect performances of SACCOs operating in Garissa County.

Research Objective

- i. To evaluate the effects of liquidity management practices on performance of SACCOs in Garissa County

Research Hypothesis

- i. *There is no significant effect of liquidity management practices on performance of SACCOs in Garissa County*

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Liquidity Preference Theory was developed by J.M Keynes in 1983 and suggests that an increased liquidity preference equates to increased money demand and thus money demands heightens anytime individuals bear a thought of a possible rise in interest rate. The individuals' demand for money was

hypothesized to depend on the foregone interest without holding bonds construed to represent stocks or less liquid assets. The theory postulates that individuals and firms holds money with different motives. The motives may comprise of precautionary, transactions or speculative. In the transaction motive, individuals bear the perception that income is acquired periodically thus a portion of the received income need to be kept till the next income is received so as to be in a position to execute transactions. Jossa(2021) adds that transaction motive further includes business motive as it suggests that there is time involved prior making sales in the market but despite this, the institutions has to be in a position of paying employees, acquiring production materials and executing other financial transactions as they may be required. This calls for availability of cash for this purpose. The precautionary motive entails keeping aside some funds for meeting unforeseen emergencies and situations. In the speculative motive, an institution sets aside money to speculate on the probable changes in areas of interest rates with a view of making profits.

The theory stipulates that investors have preferences on short term preferences as compared to long term securities (Lavoie and Reissl, 2018). As an encouragement to the investors to hold long term bonds, there is a need for the long term securities to yield more interests as compared to short term securities. The theory expounds more on liquidity practices that majority of investors prefer. Investors go for prolonged securities as they yield high levels of profits. SACCOs benefit more when they possess investments with more interest acquired from investments which call for receivables to very low for the business to achieve liquidity aspects.

Liquidity Management Practices and Financial Performance

Liquidity management has of late received serious attention worldwide especially due to the prevailing financial situations and the dynamics in the world economy. Patjoshi (2018) views liquidity as an organization's ability of meeting obligations in short terms. It also refers to the ability of the organization of converting its assets in its possession to cash. The main concern of business managers and owners worldwide is to formulate strategies for managing daily organizational operations aiming at meeting their obligations as they occur and increasing the wealth of stakeholders as well as profitability. Assets

liquidity entails how fast and quickly the asset can be converted into cash.

When referring to organizational liquidity, an individual generally means the ability of the organization of meeting its prevailing liabilities and it is usually assessed through various financial ratios. In most cases, management of liquidity is viewed from the perspective of working capital since majority of indices utilized in assessing liquidity of the firm tends to be functions of working capital components. Arief(2021) notes that liquidity management forms a crucial decision area of financial management that call for careful planning and handling for the organization to be profitable and successful. The importance attached to liquidity management is that it bears an effect on the financial performance of organization. An organization should strive to ensure it does not encounter suffering from lacking excess liquidity for meeting its compulsions in the short terms.

SACCOs generate money through mobilizing deposits in short-terms at reduced rates of interest or through investing the funds in long terms but in high rates of interests thus necessitating for good assets and liability management. Poor management of liquidity according to Otwoko and Maina(2021) exposes the financial institutions to risks in liquidity management which bears a negative or positive impact on the institution's performance. Kimathi *et al.*, (2021) while assessing factors that affect liquidity risk management practices focusing on micro finances in Kenya, Otwoko and Maina(2021) established that liquidity risk management accelerates growth of the micro finances operating in Kenya. SACCOs are usually associated with consideration to their abilities of meeting collateral, cash or liquidity requirements without incurring heavy process costs.

Liquidity management thus forms one of the critical aspects that management of SACCOs ought to take a careful consideration. Mwashu and Miroga (2018) notes that some SACCOs possess high liquidity aiming at foregoing some investment costs with capability of fetching return values. The profitability of SACCOs closely relates with adequacy in the levels of liquidity which in many SACCOs is portrayed through contributions made by customers and the ration on total assets and customers' contributions to total ratio of loans. Experience indication in the trade offs between return risk and liquidity is shown by the SACCOs returns through diverting from securities in the short terms to loans in

the long terms which tends to increase the institution's liquidity risks. SACCOs therefore with high ratios of liquidity bear low profits and reduced risks (Mwashu & Miroga, 2018).

Managing funds effectively demands the financial institutions to plan and estimate demands of liquidity over various periods and considering how requirements for funding may arise from various scenarios even in adverse operational conditions. There is a need for SACCOs to maintain sufficient cash levels, prospective lines of borrowing and liquid assets to meet contingent and expected liquidity demands. Liquidity management in the operations of SACCOs is a crucial component for realizing sound and safe financial management thus performance (Kimathi *et al.*, 2021).

Sound management of liquidity entails managing liabilities and assets prudently both as to concentration and cash flow aiming at ensuring that cash inflows bear appropriate associations to approaching outflow cash. This calls for support through a liquidity planning process which tends to assess potential liquidity needs in the future, considering dynamism in the economy, operating environment and regulatory framework. Such planning entails identifying expected, known and potential outflow of cash and weighing alternative liability/assets strategies of management aiming at ensuring that adequate inflows of cash shall be available to the financial institution to meet the needs(Kimathi *et al.*, 2021)..

2.3 Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework comprises of networks of concepts linked together to provide a broad understanding of a certain phenomenon. The framework provides structure and content for the whole study. Sekaran and Bougie(2013) defined a conceptual framework as a set of extensive ideas and philosophy taken from pertinent areas of study and used to constitute a subsequent presentation. Figure 2.1 presents the conceptual framework that was adopted in the study. The independent variables of the study comprised of liquidity management practices, working capital management, investment decision practices and financial reporting practices while performance of SACCOs represents the dependent variable.

Independent Variables

Dependent Variables

2.0 Empirical Literature Review

This section seeks to provide a review of past studies in relation to the practice and its impacts on performances of firms in various contexts. The study employed a descriptive research design and targeted 4460 SMEs operating in Lagos.

3. Research Methodology

Research Design

According to Saunders et al., (2014), a research design is the consistent and logical arrangement of numerous research components in order to successfully address the questions posed in the study and blend the relevance of research goal with economic consequences. A descriptive research design was used in the current study. According to Kothari (2011), the purpose of this study strategy is to provide explanations for facts relevant to the existence and occurrence of distinct

phenomena. The current study's design is appropriate because it depicts the existing situation and the researcher has no influence over the variables.

Target Population

According to Mugenda & Mugenda (2013), a target population is an entire set of things or people that the study seeks to assess and examine in order to generalize conclusions and findings to other related populations. The current study focused on SACCOs in Garissa County. According to the Garissa County Government, the county has ten registered SACCOs. The study included all of the SACCOs. Each SACCO's observation unit was made up of employees from the top, medium, and lower management levels. The survey included 115 employees in all. The study's target population is shown in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Target Population

Target Population	Population	Percentage
Top Level	15	13.1%
Middle Level	30	26.2%
Lower Level	70	60.7%
Total	115	100%

Source: Garissa County Government

Sampling Design and Procedure

The sampling technique refers to the approach or methodology used in selecting units to participate in the study. The study used a census method. Festinger, DeMatteo, and Marczyk (2013) advocate for the use of a census approach in small populations to ensure that all units are included in the study. The study ruled out the use of a sampling technique because it used a census approach.

Data Analysis and Presentation

In order to summarize the data and manipulate the data to address the research question(s), data analysis is described as a series of connected operations carried out on the data that have been collected (Kothari, 2013). The data is cleansed for uniformity, quality, and completeness when the data collecting procedure is complete. Before conducting the final analysis, the data is then compiled, arranged, coded, and tabulated. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were applied to analyze the data. Descriptive

statistics comprised of standard deviation, means and percentages while inferential statistics comprises of regression and correlation analysis. SPSS computer software version 24 and excel was employed to generate both the descriptive and inferential statistics. The results of the study was summarized and presented through figures and tables. The study adopts the following multivariate model was applied in the study to establish the relationship between financial management practices and performance of SACCOs.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \varepsilon$$

Where;

Y = Performance of SACCOs

X₁ = Liquidity Management Practices

ε = Error term

β_0 = Regression constant or intercept,

β_1 , is the unknown coefficients of independent variable.

4.0 Research Findings and Discussion

Demographic Characteristics Results

Highest Level of Education

According to the findings on the respondents' highest educational level, which are depicted in figure 4.2, 23.5% of the respondents were certificate holders, 40.9% had a diplomas, 28.4% had a degrees, and 7.2% had a were post graduates. The findings indicate that the majority of respondents have a diplomas or other advanced education. The findings imply that all study participants were educated, in a position to comprehend the questionnaire's contents, and in a position to respond appropriately.

Figure 4.2: Highest Level of Education

Respondents Position

According to the findings on respondents' position, shown in figure 4.3, 62.4% of respondents occupied lower managerial positions, 26.7% occupied middle level managerial positions while 10.9% occupies the

top level managerial positions. The findings indicate that the lower level managerial positions made up the bulk of the respondents. However, the study included participants from every department.

Figure 4.3 Respondents Position

Respondents Experience

According to the respondent experience findings shown in figure 4.4, there were 26.6% of respondents with experience of one year or less, 31.8% with experience of one to three years, 28.5% with experience of three to five years, and 13.1% with experience of more than five years. The results

indicate that the majority of respondents had experience of three years or more, indicating that they had worked for a considerable amount of time in Saccos to comprehend the Sacco's financial management methods and their impact on financial performance.

Figure 4.4: Respondents Experience

Descriptive Statistics

In order to describe the distribution of measures derived from responses to items contained in each variable in the questionnaire, the study used descriptive statistics. Both means and standard deviations were included in the study's descriptive statistics. The researcher asked the respondents to rate their levels of agreement with regard to the items included in each of the variables on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 denoting "strongly disagree," 2 denoting "disagree," 3 denoting "neutral," 4 denoting "agree," and 5 denoting "strongly agree." The researcher collected the standard deviations and mean replies for each of the assertions. The average answer means and average standard deviations served as the foundation for the results.

current liabilities (mean=4.28, std.dev=0.199). The respondents also agreed that the Sacco maintains liquidity ratios at optimal levels (mean=3.87, std.dev=0.921), that cash budgets are prepared in the Sacco (mean=4.53, std.dev=0.126), that the Sacco has an optimal policy on cash balance (mean=4.05, std.dev=0.309), and that there is regular assessment of both the minimum liquidity level and the optimum liquidity level, as shown by means of 4.13 and 0.271 respectively. An average response of 4.15 and average standard deviation of 0.323 indicates that all respondents agreed with the statements on liquidity management practices. The results concurs with Arief (2021) who noted that liquidity management forms a crucial decision area of financial management that call for careful planning and handling for the organization to be profitable and successful.

Liquidity Management Practices

The descriptive findings about practices for managing liquidity are shown in Table 4.2. The findings showed that respondents agreed with the claims that their Sacco maintains a high level of current assets in comparison to current liabilities (mean=4.07, std.dev=0.263), that Sacco maintains a higher level of cash securities than current liabilities (mean=4.11, std.dev=0.244), and that Sacco maintains a higher level of marketable securities than

Table 4.2: Descriptive Statistics on Liquidity Management Practices

Statements	Mean	Std.Dev
Our Sacco maintains a high level of current assets as compared to current liabilities	4.07	0.263
Our Sacco maintains higher cash securities than current liabilities	4.11	0.244
Our Sacco maintains higher marketable securities than current liabilities	4.28	0.199
Our Sacco maintains liquidity ratios at optimal levels	3.87	0.921
There is preparation of cash budgets in our Sacco	4.53	0.126
Our Sacco has an optimum policy on cash balance	4.05	0.309
Our Sacco regularly assesses minimum liquidity levels	4.13	0.276
Our Sacco regularly assesses optimum liquidity levels	4.16	0.271
Average	4.15	0.323

Source: Researcher(2023)

Table 4.3: Correlation Analysis

		Liquidity Management Practices	Financial Performance
Liquidity Management Practices	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.275	
Financial Performance	Pearson Correlation	0.578**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	90	90

Multiple Regression Analysis

The study included a multiple regression analysis with the aim of establish the nature of relationships between financial management practices and financial performance. The analysis was conducted at 95% level of confident. The model summary evaluates the degree of relationship between the total number of independent variables and the dependent variable as well as the contribution of independent variables to the dependent variable. According to the

model summary result shown in table 4.8, there is a strong correlation between SACCO financial performance in Garissa County and its financial management techniques. R-value of 0.847 demonstrates this. The data also demonstrate that financial management practices, which include practices for managing liquidity, working capital, investments, and financial reporting, account for 71.4% of the total, as shown by an R-square value (coefficient of determination) of 0.714.

Table 4.4: Model Summary

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.847 ^a	0.714	0.672	0.079248

Predictors: (Constant), Liquidity Management Practices, In order to determine whether the model connecting financial management practices with financial performance was statistically significant, analysis of variance or model significance was also included in the study. The level of significance is determined by comparing the values of F-Calculated and F-Critical from the F-Statistics table at a significance level of

0.05 and (4,85), respectively. The data shown in table 4.5 indicate that the F-Calculated value was 11.2888 and the F-Critical value was 2.49. The model's F-calculated value is higher than its F-Critical value, indicating that it is statistically significant in evaluating the relationship.

Table 4.6: ANOVA (Model Significance)

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	129.207	4	32.30175	11.2888	0.02212 ^b
Residual	243.219	85	2.8614		
Total	372.426	89			

Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

Predictors: (Constant), Liquidity Management Practices,

The study further included the regression coefficient to assess how the dependent variable change as a results of a unit change in the independent variable. The results outlined in table 4.7shows that the financial performance of Saccos operating in Garissa County is positively and significantly affected by liquidity management practices. This is demonstrated by a beta value of 0.491 and significance value of

0.000<0.05. The result implies that when liquidity management practices in increased by one unit, financial performance of the Saccos increases with 0.491 units. Liquidity management in the operations of SACCOS is a crucial component for realizing sound and safe financial management thus performance (Kimathi *et al.*, 2021).

Table 4.7: Model Coefficients

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
(Constant)	0.843	0.121		6.9670	0.000
Liquidity Management Practices	0.491	0.104	0.416	4.7212	0.000

Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

5.0 Summary of Findings, Conclusions and Recommendations

Summary of the Findings

The study focused on evaluating the effect of liquidity management practices, on financial performance. The study targeted 10 SACCOS operating in Garissa County. The unit of observation comprised of employees from top, middle and lower management levels of each of the SACCOS. A total of 115 employees were involved in the study.

According to the findings of the descriptive analysis, every respondent agreed with the statements made regarding liquidity management strategies and their impact on Saccos' financial success.

Conclusion

The study's findings led to the conclusion that the financial performance of Saccos in Garissa County is significantly and positively impacted by practices related to liquidity management. As a result, the Saccos' procedures for managing liquidity such as

maintaining a high level of current assets as compared to current liabilities, maintaining higher cash securities than current liabilities and higher marketable securities than current liabilities, maintaining liquidity ratios at optimal levels, preparing cash budgets, having an optimum policy on cash balance, regularly assessing minimum liquidity levels and optimum liquidity levels further contributes to improved financial performance of Saccos in Garissa County.

Recommendations

The study provides recommendation to the management of Saccos operating in Garissa County to enhance their liquidity management practices since the practice bears a positive and significance effect on financial performance. Saccos can realize this through adopting liquidity management practices such as maintaining a high level of current assets as compared to current liabilities, maintaining higher cash securities than current liabilities and higher marketable securities than current liabilities, maintaining liquidity ratios at optimal levels,

preparing cash budgets, having an optimum policy on cash balance, regularly assessing minimum liquidity levels and optimum liquidity levels.

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